

Diagnostic Value of the ALT/LDH Ratio in Acute Liver Injury: A Case of Misleading Acetaminophen Exposure

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Abstract

Acetaminophen is widely used for the treatment of pain and fever but is known to cause hepatotoxicity, particularly at high doses or in the presence of predisposing factors. Distinguishing acetaminophen-induced liver injury from acute viral hepatitis may be challenging due to overlapping clinical and biochemical features.

We report the case of a 25-year-old man presenting with malaise, epigastralgia, and fever, who had taken therapeutic doses of acetaminophen prior to admission. Laboratory findings revealed markedly elevated liver enzymes, raising suspicion of acute toxic hepatitis. However, subsequent serological testing confirmed acute hepatitis B infection.

During hospitalization, the patient was treated with N-acetylcysteine and supportive care. Serial monitoring of liver enzymes and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) levels, including the ALT/LDH ratio, helped differentiate between toxic and viral liver injury phases. The patient showed progressive clinical improvement and complete normalization of liver function at follow-up.

This case highlights the diagnostic challenges in distinguishing drug-induced liver injury from viral hepatitis and underscores the importance of integrating clinical history, laboratory findings, and dynamic biochemical markers in the diagnostic process.

Keywords: Acetaminophen; Drug-induced liver injury; Viral hepatitis; Hepatitis B; ALT/LDH ratio.

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INTRODUCTION

Acetaminophen (paracetamol) is widely used for the treatment of pain and fever and is generally considered safe at therapeutic doses. However, hepatotoxicity may occur at doses exceeding 4 g/day or even at lower doses in the presence of predisposing factors such as chronic alcohol use, malnutrition, or underlying liver disease [1].

Acute viral hepatitis represents another common cause of liver injury and may present with nonspecific symptoms, often leading patients to self-medicate with acetaminophen during the prodromal phase.

The coexistence of these conditions may complicate the diagnostic process, as clinical and biochemical findings may overlap. In particular, distinguishing between drug-induced liver injury and viral hepatitis is crucial for appropriate management.

We report a case highlighting the diagnostic challenges in differentiating acetaminophen-related hepatotoxicity from acute viral hepatitis.

CASE REPORT

A 25-year-old man, born in Sri Lanka, presented to the Emergency Department with a 3-day history of malaise, asthenia, epigastralgia, and fever. His medical history was unremarkable. He reported unprotected sexual intercourse in the preceding months and denied alcohol consumption or recreational drug use.

For symptom relief, he had taken seven tablets of acetaminophen (paracetamol), each containing 1,000 mg, over the previous two days.

On admission, vital signs were stable. Physical examination was unremarkable except for mild epigastric tenderness. There were no signs of jaundice, rash, or lymphadenopathy.

Laboratory investigations revealed markedly elevated liver enzymes: alanine aminotransferase (ALT) 1,375 U/L and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) 1,004 U/L. Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) was 2,178 U/L, with an ALT/LDH ratio of 0.63. Total bilirubin was 0.25 mg/dL, C-reactive protein (CRP) 3 mg/L, and white blood cell count 2,800/mm³ (42% lymphocytes). The prothrombin time (INR) was 0.95. Abdominal ultrasonography was normal.

Based on these findings, the patient was admitted with a provisional diagnosis of acute toxic hepatitis secondary to acetaminophen exposure and was treated with N-acetylcysteine.

During hospitalization, despite persistently elevated liver enzymes, the patient remained clinically stable, with no evidence of coagulopathy or hepatic encephalopathy. Serial laboratory monitoring demonstrated sustained elevation of aminotransferases and LDH (Figure 1), with dynamic changes in the ALT/LDH ratio over time (Figure 2).

Further diagnostic evaluation included serological testing for viral infections. Results revealed acute hepatitis B infection, with positive hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) and hepatitis B core antibody (IgM). Serology for hepatitis A and C viruses, Epstein–Barr virus, and cytomegalovirus was negative for acute infection. HIV serology was positive and required further evaluation (Table 1).

Over the subsequent week, the patient's clinical condition progressively improved. Liver enzyme levels gradually decreased, and supportive therapy was continued. The patient was discharged in stable condition.

At follow-up two weeks after discharge, liver function tests had returned to normal, confirming complete biochemical recovery. No recurrence or complications were observed at short-term follow-up.

Figure 1. Serial changes in ALT, AST, and LDH levels during hospitalization, illustrating the evolution of liver injury.

Figure 2. Dynamic changes in the ALT/LDH ratio during hospitalization, highlighting its role in differentiating acetaminophen-induced liver injury from viral hepatitis [9].

Serological testing for hepatitis A, B, and C viruses, as well as Epstein–Barr virus, cytomegalovirus, and HIV, was performed (Table 1), confirming acute hepatitis B infection.

Table 1. Viral serological profile.

Virus	Test	Result
Hepatitis A	HAV-Ab (IgM)	Negative
Hepatitis B	HBs-Ag	Positive
	HBc-Ab (IgM)	Positive
	HBe-Ab	Negative
Hepatitis C	HCV-Ab	Negative
Epstein-Barr virus	AntiEBV-Ab (IgM)	Negative
	AntiEBV-Ab (IgG)	Positive
Cytomegalovirus	AntiCMV-Ab (IgM)	Negative
	AntiCMV-Ab (IgG)	Positive
HIV	Anti-HIV-Ab	Positive

The patient demonstrated progressive clinical and biochemical recovery during hospitalization and was discharged in stable condition. Complete normalization of liver function tests was observed at two-week follow-up.

DISCUSSION

Acetaminophen (paracetamol) is widely recognized as a safe and effective analgesic when used at therapeutic doses; however, hepatotoxicity may occur not only at doses exceeding 4 g/day but also at lower doses in the presence of predisposing factors [1]. These include chronic alcohol use, concomitant medications inducing hepatic enzymes, malnutrition, and underlying liver disease such as viral hepatitis [2–6].

Acute viral hepatitis may present with nonspecific prodromal symptoms, including fever, malaise, and epigastric discomfort, which often lead patients to self-medicate with acetaminophen. In this context, acetaminophen may act as a cofactor, potentially exacerbating hepatocellular injury during the early phase of viral infection [7].

The pathophysiological mechanisms underlying this interaction are complex and may involve cytokine-mediated modulation of cytochrome P450 enzyme activity during viral infections, leading to altered drug metabolism and increased susceptibility to hepatotoxicity [5,8].

From a diagnostic perspective, distinguishing acetaminophen-induced liver injury from viral hepatitis may be challenging due to overlapping clinical and biochemical features. In this setting, dynamic laboratory parameters can provide valuable support. In particular, the ALT/LDH ratio has been proposed as a useful marker: lower values are more suggestive of toxic liver injury, whereas higher values are typically associated with viral hepatitis [9].

In our case, the initial biochemical pattern, characterized by markedly elevated LDH levels and a low ALT/LDH ratio (<1.5), suggested a toxic component related to acetaminophen exposure. However, subsequent serological findings confirmed acute hepatitis B infection, and the progressive increase in the ALT/LDH ratio during hospitalization supported the transition to a predominantly viral pattern of hepatocellular injury.

This case illustrates how acetaminophen use at therapeutic doses, in the context of an unrecognized viral infection, may contribute to liver injury and complicate the diagnostic process. It also highlights the importance of integrating clinical history, risk factors, and dynamic laboratory markers in order to correctly identify the underlying etiology.

CONCLUSIONS

Acetaminophen-related hepatotoxicity and acute viral hepatitis may present with overlapping clinical and biochemical features, making differential diagnosis challenging. This case emphasizes the importance

of careful drug history assessment and the use of dynamic laboratory markers, such as the ALT/LDH ratio, in guiding diagnosis. Early recognition of the underlying etiology is essential to ensure appropriate management and avoid potential complications.

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